

Enhancing Cervical Segmentation via Alternate Diverse Teaching in Semi-supervised Learning

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Abstract—In clinical practice, the cervical structure plays a critical role in predicting preterm birth, thus making accurate segmentation of this structure in ultrasound images of paramount importance. However, the performance of existing deep learning methods is limited by the high cost of labeling ultrasound images. In this context, semi-supervised medical image segmentation techniques have emerged as promising solutions, particularly recent teacher-student frameworks that have demonstrated notable efficacy. Despite their success, these methods are often subject to confirmation bias, which undermines their reliability. To address this issue, we introduce a novel approach, Alternate Diverse Teaching (AD-MT), for the semi-supervised segmentation of cervical ultrasound images. AD-MT enhances model performance by alternately updating two teacher models, offering diverse perspectives during learning. Furthermore, a conflict-combating module is incorporated to ensure that the model learns from the discrepancies between teacher predictions. This methodology effectively harnesses both labeled and unlabeled data for segmentation tasks. Experimental results demonstrate that AD-MT achieves competitive segmentation performance, as evidenced by its strong showing in the ISBI 2025 Fetal Ultrasound Grand Challenge.

Index Terms—cervical ultrasound segmentation, semi-supervised learning, teacher-student model, Alternate Diverse Teaching

I. INTRODUCTION

Preterm birth is currently one of the leading causes of neonatal mortality in many countries [1], and cervical ultrasound imaging serves as a critical clinical tool for predicting spontaneous preterm birth and delivery. It plays a vital role in the early identification of high-risk pregnancies. Among various methods, transvaginal ultrasound is the preferred method for cervical observation in most patients, as it provides detailed insights into the anatomical structure and configuration of the cervix. Consequently, accurate segmentation of cervical muscles in ultrasound (US) images is essential for analyzing deep muscle architecture, assessing their functionality, and monitoring personalized treatment plans tailored to individual patients.

However, for transvaginal ultrasound images of the cervical structure, the traditional manual annotation process is not only time-consuming and labor-intensive but also requires the involvement of highly experienced experts, making the acquisition of large-scale segmentation annotations particularly challenging. To address this issue, semi-supervised learning (SSL), an effective machine learning approach, has seen

significant development and application in medical image segmentation tasks in recent years. Techniques such as semi-supervised learning with pseudo labels [2] [3] [4] [5] and semi-supervised learning with unsupervised regularization [6] [7] [8] [9] have been widely explored. These methods effectively leverage large amounts of unlabeled data in combination with a limited amount of labeled data, enabling the model to be trained more efficiently. By mitigating the challenges posed by the scarcity or difficulty of obtaining labeled data, SSL holds great promise for automating the segmentation of cervical ultrasound images.

Recent semi-supervised methods applied to medical imaging primarily focus on consistency regularization (CR) approaches, which reduce model discrepancies by generating consistent predictions on the same unlabeled input [10] [11]. However, single models often produce noisy or incorrect pseudo-labels, leading to confirmation bias [12]. This situation can lead to the model becoming overly confident in its incorrect predictions and overestimating its performance. To address this issue, the multi-teacher ensemble has become an effective method, which iteratively updates different teacher models to avoid additional training overhead. However, previous multi-teacher ensemble methods [19] [20] often use a fixed approach in the pseudo-label generation process, without considering the features of the input samples, resulting in lower-quality pseudo-labels. In particular, these methods often lack effective strategies for teacher model updates, and most approaches focus solely on consistent predictions while neglecting the potential of conflicting predictions.

To address these challenges, we introduce a novel method called AD-MT, an alternate diverse teaching approach in a teacher-student framework [13]. The core of this method lies in two introduced modules: the Random Periodic Alternate (RPA) update module and the Conflict-Combating Module (CCM). In this way, the model can benefit from the reasoning of teachers from different teaching perspectives and learn from both the consistent and conflicting predictions between the teachers, alleviating the issue of confirmation bias and achieving better segmentation performance.

In this paper, we focus on training the model using the AD-MT method with both labeled and unlabeled data to achieve precise segmentation of the anterior lip and posterior lip of the cervix in transvaginal ultrasound images. Our approach

Fig. 1. The schematic of AD-MT consists of two main modules: the Random Periodic Alternate (RPA) update Module and the Conflict-Combating Module (CCM). During the training process, the two teacher models, T1 and T2, are updated in turn periodically and randomly.

has yielded competitive results in the fetal ultrasound grand challenge in ISBI 2025 Challenges.

II. METHOD

In this section, we introduce the semi-supervised training framework AD-MT adopted in our study, followed by a detailed description of its two main components: the Random Periodic Alternate (RPA) Update Module and the Conflict-Combating Module (CCM).

A. AD-MT Structure

Given a labeled set $D_l = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^{N_l}$ with N_l samples and an unlabeled set $D_u = \{x_i\}_{i=1}^{N_u}$ with N_u samples, where $N_u \gg N_l$ in semi-supervised task.

As shown in Fig. 1, the overall structure of AD-MT consists of a single student model parameterized by θ_s and two auxiliary teacher models parameterized by θ_{t_1} and θ_{t_2} . The student model receives gradients for backpropagation, while the teacher models are alternately updated through the exponential moving average (EMA) of the student model's weights.

Pseudo label generation. Although Teacher 1 (T1) and Teacher 2 (T2) are updated alternately, both teacher models participate in pseudo-label generation for unlabeled data in each iteration. Specifically, using $a(\cdot)$ to denote weak augmentation operations (random cropping and flipping), pseudo-labels can be generated for each unlabeled sample u_i as follows:

- $q_i^{t_1} = f(a(u_i); \theta_{t_1})$: Generated by T1 based on the weakly augmented input.
- $q_i^{t_2} = f(a(u_i); \theta_{t_2})$: Generated by T2 using the same augmentation as T1.
- $q_i^s = f(a(u_i); \theta_s)$: The prediction of the student model on the same augmented sample.

The final pseudo-label is formulated as:

$$q_i = \phi(q_i^{t_1}, q_i^{t_2}, q_i^s; \tau) \quad (1)$$

Where $\phi(\cdot)$ represents the function of the proposed Conflict-Combating Module, and τ denotes the predefined high-confidence threshold.

Loss function. The student model can be trained directly on labeled data using standard supervised loss \mathcal{L}_x .

$$\mathcal{L}_x = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}_x|} \sum_{i=1}^B \frac{1}{H \times W} \sum_{j=1}^{H \times W} \ell(\hat{y}_i(j), y_i(j)), \quad (2)$$

where \hat{y}_i denotes the student model's prediction on the i -th labeled data x_i , i.e., $\hat{y}_i = f(x_i; \theta_s)$, and j represents the j -th pixel on the image or the corresponding segmentation mask with a resolution of $H \times W$.

The conflict-combating consistency loss \mathcal{L}_u is applied to the unlabeled data.

$$\mathcal{L}_u = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}_u|} \sum_{i=1}^{\mu B} \frac{1}{H \times W} \sum_{j=1}^{H \times W} \ell(p_i(j), q_i(j)), \quad (3)$$

Where $p_i = f(A_m(u_i); \theta_s)$ represents the prediction of the student model on the strongly augmented unlabeled data $A_m(u_i)$. $A_m \in \{A1, A2\}$, with $m = 1, 2$, denoting two different strong data augmentation strategies, each corresponding to the alternate turn of T1 and T2. The entire updating strategy is executed by the Random Periodic Alternate Module.

Finally, the total training loss is given by:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_x + \lambda_t \mathcal{L}_u, \quad (4)$$

Where λ_t is a function related to the iteration that adjusts the importance of the consistency loss \mathcal{L}_u .

B. Random Periodic Alternate Updating Module

In each iteration, only one of the two teacher models is updated. Throughout the entire training period, unique and complementary batches of unlabeled data are used to refine the two teacher models, ensuring that their updates are distinct, allowing them to complement each other's learning during the training process. To further increase the diversity of the two teacher models, the color-jittering operation [14] is applied to the augmentation of T1, while the copy-paste augmentation [15] is applied to T2. On the other hand, to increase the randomness of the alternating mode, the alternating period for each teacher is randomly generated when a switch occurs. Specifically:

$$T_m \leftarrow \text{random.randint}(0, T_{\max}), m \in \{1, 2\}$$

where T_m represents the alternating update period for each teacher model (in terms of iterations), with $m \in \{1, 2\}$ and T_{\max} denoting the predefined maximum period.

In this way, the RPA module not only increases the diversity between the two teacher models but also reduces the risk of excessive data perturbation.

C. Conflict-Combating Module

The Conflict-Combating Module is designed to address the issue of conflicting predictions between the two teacher models, which is abstracted as the function $\phi(\cdot)$. Rather than directly discarding these conflicts, the CCM encourages the model to further learn from the discrepancies with the assistance of the student model.

The CCM module first separates the consistent and conflicting predictions between the two teacher models. On one hand, it applies the entropy-based teacher ensemble on the unlabeled instance u_i to obtain an ensemble prediction ψ_i , which is directly used for consistent supervision. Given the entropy of the predictions from the two teacher models (denoted as $H(\cdot)$),

$$H_{t_1} = H(q_i^{t_1}) = - \sum_{i=1}^C q_i^{t_1} \log_2 q_i^{t_1}, \quad (5)$$

$$H_{t_2} = H(q_i^{t_2}) = - \sum_{i=1}^C q_i^{t_2} \log_2 q_i^{t_2}, \quad (6)$$

the entropy-based ensemble prediction can be expressed as,

$$\psi_i = \psi(q_i^{t_1}, q_i^{t_2}) = \frac{w_1 q_i^{t_1} + w_2 q_i^{t_2}}{w_1 + w_2}, \quad (7)$$

Where $w_1 = e^{-H_{t_1}}$ and $w_2 = e^{-H_{t_2}}$. Considering the continuous improvement of the student model, we compare the entropy of the student prediction with the entropy of the ensemble prediction. The final supervision for conflicting predictions is based on the lower entropy. The final prediction q_i is given by:

$$q_i(j) = \begin{cases} I(\max(q_i^s(j)) \geq \tau) q_i^s(j), & \text{if } q_i^{t_1} \neq q_i^{t_2} \text{ and } H_{\psi_i(j)} > H_{q_i^s(j)} \\ I(\max(\psi_i(j)) \geq \tau) \psi_i(j), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where $I(\cdot)$ is used to select high-confidence predictions for the unlabeled supervision.

III. EXPERIMENT

A. Dataset

The FUGC dataset is provided by the Fetal Ultrasound Grand Challenge in ISBI 2025 and contains transvaginal ultrasound images of the cervix after bladder emptying. The images are captured using a curved transducer with a frequency range of 2 to 10 MHz (for cervical ultrasound screening in mid-gestation patients). The dataset includes 450 unlabeled images and 50 labeled images, with annotations covering the cervical anatomical structures (the anterior and posterior lips of the cervix).

B. Evaluation Metrics

- **Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC):** DSC is a commonly used metric in medical image segmentation, which measures the overlap between the predicted segmentation and the ground truth. It quantifies the similarity between two sets, with a value range of (0, 1).
- **Hausdorff Distance (HD):** The Hausdorff Distance is used to evaluate the boundary error between the predicted and ground truth segmentations. It measures the maximum distance between a point on one boundary and the closest point on the other boundary. The Hausdorff Distance is sensitive to outliers and provides an indication of how well the model captures the boundary structure of the object.
- **Running Time:** Running time is measured to evaluate the inference speed of the model. This metric is important for assessing the efficiency of the model in real-world applications, where fast processing is often required, especially in clinical settings.

C. Implementation Details

For all experiments, we use U-Net [16] as the segmentation model, with an input patch size of 256x256. We select 10 out of the 50 labeled images as the validation set and choose the model that performs best on the validation set after training as the final model. The batch size is set to 24, and the training runs for 60k iterations. We use the SGD optimizer to train the student model with polynomial learning rate decay, where the initial learning rate is 0.01 multiplied by $(1 - \text{iter}/\text{max_iter})^{0.9}$. The momentum and weight decay are set to 0.9 and 0.0001 respectively. Two teacher models are randomly initialized and updated with an exponential parameter of 0.99. Additionally, we use the default settings for AD-MT, with the maximum loss weight $\lambda_u = 2.0$ and the maximum cycle $T_m = 0.5$ epoch for all runs.

D. Experimental Results

We introduce several semi-supervised segmentation methods proposed in recent years to the task setup of this challenge, including Mean Teacher (MT) [17] and Deep Co-Training [18]. All competing methods use the official parameter settings.

TABLE I

Method	Val		Test		
	Dice	HD	Dice	HD	Run time
MT	0.923	65.26	0.752	96.04	6.97
DCT	0.948	21.57	0.754	59.14	5.57
AD-MT	0.954	13.32	0.879	36.83	6.97

Tab. I shows the performance of different methods on the segmentation of the anterior lip and posterior lip of the cervix in transvaginal ultrasound images. "Val" in the table represents the performance on the validation set, while "Test" represents the performance on the test set during the validation phase

Fig. 2. Visual comparison of segmentation results with different methods.

of the challenge. The Run time on the test set is provided by the competition platform. Clearly, AD-MT outperforms all other methods. We present the segmentation results of different methods in Fig. 2, which reflect that the approach we used achieves more accurate segmentation of the target classes. In addition, to achieve better generalization performance, we replaced the segmentation model with UNet++ [21]. The final results obtained in the validation phase were as follows: Dice of 0.892, HD of 30.85, and run time of 22.20.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we apply the AD-MT method to Semi-Supervised Cervical Segmentation. Specifically, this method ensures that the two teacher models are updated in different ways through the application of various strategies, complementing each other throughout the training process. Additionally, the designed conflict combination strategy encourages the model to learn from the discrepancies between the teachers. Thanks to the effectiveness of the method, our approach achieved a high ranking in the FUGC challenge at ISBI 2025.

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